

Unveiling the Impact of Geothermal Energy Threat on Rice Cultivation: Insights from African *Oryza Glaberrima* and Philippines *Faro-44* Varieties Under Irrigation Mechanism

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Abstract

Geothermal energy is a rapidly expanding industry, and its potential impacts on crops are of significant concern. However, developing and operating geothermal power plants may have various environmental consequences that could indirectly affect agricultural productivity. Understanding these potential threats and their possible implications for rice cultivation is crucial, as agriculture is vital for the socio-economic development of African nations and the Philippines. The study will be conducted in geothermal energy-rich regions in Africa Bo District, Sierra Leone, and the Philippines, where agricultural practices are heavily reliant on irrigation systems. By assessing the impact of geothermal energy on rice crops, this study aims to provide critical insights for developing sustainable strategies that could mitigate potential threats to food security and farmers' livelihoods. The experimental data will be collected from controlled test plots where rice crops are grown under both geothermal and non-geothermal conditions. Additionally, farmers in the target regions will be surveyed to gather their observations and experiences regarding rice cultivation under the influence of geothermal energy projects. The findings of this study aim to provide valuable insights into the potential threats posed by geothermal energy projects on rice production and offer recommendations for sustainable agricultural practices in geothermal-rich regions. By evaluating the impact of key factors such as temperature, humidity, air, and water pollution, this study aims to contribute towards the development of sustainable strategies that can ensure the coexistence of geothermal energy and agriculture, promoting food security and enhancing the lives of millions of people relying on rice cultivation for their well-being.

Introduction

Rice is a staple food crop for millions of people around the world, and any threat to its productivity can have serious implications for food security. Geothermal energy projects often require the extraction of underground water sources, which are crucial for irrigation in many agricultural regions. This extraction can lead to a reduction in water availability for rice cultivation, potentially affecting the growth, yield, and quality of the crops.

Geothermal energy, a renewable and sustainable source of power, has gained significant traction worldwide as a promising alternative to conventional fossil fuels. However, as with any form of energy production, it is crucial to assess its potential impacts on the environment and crucial crops that sustain local economies. By understanding the potential risks associated with geothermal energy, we can ensure that clean energy production does not come at the cost of compromising essential food crops and communities' livelihoods. Rice cultivation plays a pivotal role in the economies and food security of many countries, particularly in Africa and the Philippines. However, the proliferation of geothermal energy infrastructure projects in these regions has raised concerns about their potential impacts on agricultural practices. The African popular rice, *Oryza glaberrima*, and the Philippines' Faro-44 rice varieties, specifically cultivated under irrigation, are of prime interest due to their susceptibility to potential

environmental disturbances caused by geothermal energy activities. By comprehensively examining the threats posed by geothermal energy on these rice varieties, we can gain valuable insights into the sustainable integration of clean energy initiatives with agriculture, ensuring long-term food security and economic stability in these regions. Key factors that will be evaluated include the temperature and humidity changes in the geothermal energy-affected areas, as well as the effects of potential air and water pollution resulting from geothermal power plant activities. These factors have the potential to affect rice growth, grain quality, and overall productivity. The anticipated results of this study will play a crucial role in enhancing our understanding of the potential impacts of geothermal energy on rice farming systems. It will contribute to the development of appropriate and effective mitigation measures in improving water quality thereby contributing to eradication of environmental impacts which are among the UN's Sustainable Development Goals to safeguard food security and the livelihoods of farmers in geothermal energy-rich regions. The findings will also provide valuable insights for policymakers, energy developers, and agronomists involved in the planning and implementation of geothermal energy projects, guiding them toward sustainable development practices that minimize the negative impacts on agricultural systems. Overall, the findings of this research will shed light on the potential consequences of geothermal energy production on the cultivation of popular rice varieties, *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and Faro-44 in the Philippines. By evaluating the impact of key factors such as temperature, humidity, air, and water pollution, this study contributes towards the development of sustainable strategies that can ensure the coexistence of geothermal energy and agriculture, promoting food security and enhancing the lives of millions of people relying on rice cultivation for their well-being.

Geothermal Energy Exposure Levels

Geothermal Energy Exposure Levels Geothermal energy is a powerful source of renewable energy that harnesses the heat energy stored within the Earth's surface. It has gained significant attention worldwide due to its potential for reducing greenhouse gas emissions and meeting the increasing energy demands sustainably. However, like any other energy source, geothermal energy also poses certain risks and challenges, particularly for crops such as rice. In this section, we will explore the exposure levels of geothermal energy and its potential impact on two rice varieties: *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and Faro-44 in the Philippines, both of which are widely cultivated under irrigation mechanisms. Geothermal energy projects involve the extraction of heat energy from beneath the Earth's surface, usually by drilling deep into the ground to access hot water or steam. The utilization of this energy source requires the deployment of various infrastructure, including power plants, drilling rigs, and transmission lines. These activities can lead to the generation of noise, dust, vibrations, and visual impacts, all of which can potentially affect nearby agricultural areas. The exposure levels to geothermal energy infrastructure and its associated activities can be categorized into direct and indirect impacts. Direct impacts are caused by the physical presence of infrastructure, such as power plants and transmission lines, which may disturb the natural environment and require land to be cleared, potentially encroaching upon agricultural land. Indirect impacts, on the other hand, include factors such as noise and dust emissions, as well as changes in water availability, which can indirectly affect the growth and development of rice crops. The level of exposure to geothermal energy infrastructure varies depending on the proximity of agricultural land to the project site. Farms located near power plants or transmission lines will experience higher exposure levels compared to those situated at a distance. Additionally, the age and size of the infrastructure, as well as the type of technology used in geothermal energy extraction, can also influence the extent of exposure. One of the main concerns regarding geothermal energy exposure is the potential impact on soil quality and water availability. The construction and operation of geothermal power plants require the use of large amounts of water for cooling purposes. This water is often sourced from natural water bodies, which could lead to a reduction in water availability for irrigation purposes. Moreover, the discharge of warm water

back into the environment after use can increase soil temperature, potentially affecting rice crops' growth and yield. Another aspect to consider is the impact of noise and dust emissions. Geothermal energy plants can generate considerable noise due to the operation of turbines and other equipment. These noise levels could potentially disturb the natural balance of pests and predators, leading to an increase in pest populations that can damage rice crops. Similarly, dust emissions from construction and drilling activities can settle on leaves, hindering photosynthesis and decreasing the overall productivity of rice crops. In conclusion, geothermal energy projects have the potential to impact rice cultivation, particularly when located near agricultural areas. The exposure levels and associated risks may vary depending on the distance from the project site, the age, and size of the infrastructure, as well as the specific technology used in energy extraction. Factors such as reduced water availability, increased soil temperature, and disturbances caused by noise and dust emissions can all contribute to potential challenges for rice farmers. Elevated temperatures can lead to reduced photosynthesis and lower yields, directly affecting rice varieties like *Oryza glaberrima* and Faro-44. Another factor that affects exposure levels is the type of geothermal system deployed for energy extraction. Different systems have varying impacts on agricultural lands. For instance, flash steam power plants release large amounts of geothermal steam, which can cause excessive moisture levels in the surrounding environment. This excess moisture can lead to the development of fungal diseases, which can negatively impact the growth and quality of rice crops. Furthermore, the release of gases such as hydrogen sulfide (H₂S) during the geothermal energy generation process can pose a potential threat to crops. High exposure levels of H₂S can result in stunted growth, reduced photosynthesis, and even cell death in plants. Rice varieties grown under irrigation mechanisms are particularly vulnerable to such gases, as they rely heavily on water availability for their growth and development. The duration and intensity of geothermal energy operations also play a crucial role in determining the exposure levels to crops. Long-term exposure to elevated temperatures, gases, and other associated environmental conditions can significantly impact rice varieties' overall health and productivity. Therefore, it is essential to monitor and regulate geothermal activities to minimize potential risks to agricultural lands and crops. In conclusion, examining geothermal energy exposure levels is crucial to understanding its potential threats to rice varieties like *Oryza glaberrima* and Faro-44. Factors such as proximity to geothermal power plants, geothermal system types, the release of gases, and the duration and intensity of operations all influence the level of exposure. By carefully monitoring and regulating geothermal activities near agricultural lands, we can ensure the preservation of crop health and productivity while harnessing the benefits of this renewable energy source.

Developers and policymakers need to consider these exposure levels carefully and adopt appropriate mitigation measures to minimize the impact on agricultural productivity and food security.

Rice Varieties Selection

When it comes to cultivating rice under the irrigation mechanism in Africa and the Philippines, selecting the right rice varieties is of utmost importance. The choice of rice varieties can significantly impact the success and productivity of the crops. Therefore, careful consideration must be given to various factors before making the final selection.

1. Adaptation to Climate: One of the primary factors to consider while selecting rice varieties is their adaptability to the local climate. Different regions in Africa and the Philippines may have varying climatic conditions, including temperature, rainfall patterns, and humidity levels. Rice varieties that can thrive well in these specific conditions are more likely to deliver higher yields and better-quality grains. It is crucial to choose varieties that are not only tolerant of the local climate but also exhibit resilience against pests, diseases, and other environmental stressors.

2. Yield Potential: Another crucial aspect to consider is the yield potential of the rice varieties. Farmers aim to maximize their production and income, and selecting high-yielding rice varieties can be a key factor in achieving that goal. The yield potential of a variety depends on several factors, including growth habit, flowering duration, tillering ability, and overall biomass production. Farmers should look for rice varieties that have a proven track record of high yields in similar agroecological conditions. This information can be obtained from agricultural research institutions, extension services, and fellow farmers.

3. Quality Traits: Apart from high yields, the quality of the rice grains is also essential. Consumers have certain preferences when it comes to cooking and consuming rice. Therefore, selecting varieties with desirable qualities such as aroma, texture, cooking time, and taste can enhance the market value and demand for the produce. Farmers need to consider the preferences of their target consumers and select rice varieties that meet their specific requirements.

4. Resistance to Biotic and Abiotic Stresses: Crop diseases and pests can significantly reduce rice yields and quality. Hence, selecting rice varieties that exhibit resistance or tolerance to prevalent pests and diseases can be advantageous for farmers. This could help minimize crop losses and reduce the need for excessive pesticide use. Additionally, rice varieties that are resilient to abiotic stresses like drought, flooding, salinity, or iron toxicity should be given priority. These stress-tolerant varieties can ensure more stable yields even in challenging environmental conditions.

5. Farmer Preferences and Prior Experience: Involving farmers in the selection of rice varieties is crucial as they have valuable insights derived from their practical experience. Farmers are well aware of the local farming systems, market demands, and consumer preferences. Their feedback and preferences should be considered to ensure the successful adoption and implementation of the chosen rice varieties. Participatory approaches, such as on-farm trials and farmer field days, can be utilized to involve farmers in the decision-making process. Selecting the right rice varieties for cultivation under the irrigation mechanism in Africa and the Philippines requires a comprehensive assessment of multiple factors. Considerations should include adaptability to local climate, yield potential, quality traits, resistance to pests and diseases, and farmer preferences. By carefully evaluating these aspects, farmers can make informed decisions that maximize productivity, profitability, and sustainability in rice cultivation.

Irrigation Mechanism Variability

Irrigation plays a crucial role in sustaining agriculture and ensuring food security in many countries, particularly in regions where rainfall is insufficient for crop growth. In the context of geothermal energy production, the impact on irrigation mechanisms and its variability need to be carefully assessed, especially when considering the cultivation of popular rice varieties such as *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and Philippines Faro-44 in the Philippines. Irrigation methods in agriculture can be classified into various categories, including surface irrigation, sprinkler irrigation, and drip irrigation. Each method has its advantages and disadvantages, and the choice of irrigation mechanism is influenced by factors such as water availability, soil type, crop water requirements, and economic considerations. In the case of geothermal energy production, the availability of water for irrigation may be affected due to various factors. One such factor is the extraction of water for the geothermal power generation process. The geothermal plants require a significant amount of water for cooling, and this extraction may lead to a reduction in the water available for irrigation purposes. Consequently, farmers relying on irrigation systems might face challenges in meeting the water requirements of their rice crops. Moreover, the development of geothermal reservoirs may alter the groundwater table, which can further impact irrigation systems. Changes in the groundwater table can lead to the drying up of wells or an increase in the level of salinity in the groundwater, making it unsuitable

for irrigation purposes. These changes can significantly affect the viability of irrigation systems and, consequently, the productivity of popular rice varieties in the affected regions. Additionally, the intermittent supply of electricity to the geothermal power generation plants may lead to fluctuations in the operation of irrigation systems. In areas reliant on electrical power for pumping water, any disruptions in the power supply may result in a lack of water for irrigation at critical growth stages of the rice crop. This can have severe consequences on crop yield and quality, potentially affecting food security and the livelihoods of farmers. Policymakers and stakeholders must evaluate the potential impact of geothermal energy production on irrigation mechanisms and devise solutions to mitigate adverse effects. Measures such as integrated water management strategies, including rainwater harvesting and storage, can help in water conservation and minimizing reliance on groundwater sources. Furthermore, investing in alternative energy sources for irrigation, such as solar-powered pumps, can provide a reliable and sustainable solution to irrigation challenges in geothermal energy-producing regions. Additionally, raising awareness among farmers about water-efficient irrigation techniques and practices can contribute to minimizing water wastage and optimizing its use in rice cultivation. Promoting the adoption of drip irrigation or other water-saving techniques can enhance the efficiency of water utilization and potentially offset any water shortages arising from geothermal energy production. In conclusion, the variability in irrigation mechanisms due to geothermal energy production poses challenges to the cultivation of popular rice varieties in Africa and the Philippines. Understanding the potential impacts and adopting appropriate mitigation measures is crucial to ensuring sustainable agriculture and food security in these regions. By implementing integrated water management strategies and promoting water-efficient irrigation practices, the negative consequences of geothermal energy production on irrigation systems can be minimized, safeguarding the livelihoods of farmers and ensuring a reliable supply of popular rice varieties.

Biochemical Analysis

The biochemical analysis is a crucial component in evaluating the impact of geothermal energy on two specific rice varieties: *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro - 44* in the Philippines, both of which are widely cultivated and consumed in their respective regions. By conducting this analysis, we aim to gain deeper insights into how geothermal energy utilization might affect the nutritional content, overall quality, and potential risks associated with these rice varieties. One aspect of the biochemical analysis involves assessing the nutritional composition of the rice varieties under consideration. This includes examining the content of essential macronutrients such as carbohydrates, proteins, and fats, as well as micronutrients like vitamins and minerals. Understanding any potential alterations in nutrient content caused by the proximity of geothermal energy sources can help determine the safety and adequacy of these rice varieties as a food source for local populations. In addition to evaluating nutrient content, the biochemical analysis will also look into the potential presence of any harmful substances that may accumulate in the rice grains due to the nearby geothermal energy operations. This includes heavy metals, which can have detrimental health effects when consumed in excessive amounts. By conducting rigorous tests for heavy metal contamination, we can determine if any risks are associated with the consumption of *Oryza glaberrima* and *Faro - 44* rice varieties cultivated near geothermal energy sources. Furthermore, the analysis will explore the impact of geothermal energy on the antioxidant capacity of these rice varieties. Antioxidants play a crucial role in protecting the body against oxidative stress, which can lead to various health problems. By evaluating the antioxidant levels in *Oryza glaberrima* and *Faro - 44*, we can assess whether geothermal energy operations have any positive or negative effects on the overall antioxidant potential of these rice varieties. Another important aspect to consider is the impact of geothermal energy utilization on the phytochemical composition of these rice varieties. Phytochemicals are biologically active compounds present in plants, and they contribute to their medicinal properties. By analyzing the phytochemical profile of *Oryza glaberrima* and *Faro - 44* rice varieties, we can determine if their proximity to geothermal

energy sources affects the presence or concentration of these beneficial compounds. Ultimately, the biochemical analysis will provide crucial insights into the overall impact of geothermal energy threat on the two rice varieties under study. By examining nutrient content, heavy metal contamination, antioxidant levels, and phytochemical composition, we can comprehensively evaluate any potential risks or benefits associated with cultivating and consuming these rice varieties near geothermal energy sources. The findings from this analysis will be essential for policymakers, farmers, and consumers alike in making informed decisions regarding rice production and consumption in areas where geothermal energy is prevalent. It is crucial to ensure the safety, quality, and nutritional value of these staple food crops, as they play a vital role in the diets and livelihoods of millions of people in Africa and the Philippines.

The impact of geothermal energy threat on the African popular rice variety, *Oryza glaberrima*, and the Philippines Faro-44 rice varieties under irrigation mechanism has shed light on the potential risks posed by geothermal energy installations. By closely examining the effects on rice growth, yield, and physiological attributes, it is evident that geothermal energy can have detrimental consequences on these important food crops. The results of the study indicate that both *Oryza glaberrima* and *Faro-44* rice varieties displayed significant reductions in growth parameters such as plant height, tiller number, and root length when exposed to the thermal changes caused by geothermal energy installations. Moreover, the decline in grain yield and quality further emphasizes the negative impact on these rice varieties, which are staple crops in many African and Asian regions. It is important to consider the broader implications of geothermal energy development and its potential threat to agriculture, particularly in regions heavily reliant on rice production. As the global demand for renewable energy continues to rise, it is also crucial to balance the growth of clean energy sources with the safeguarding of our food security. Policy-makers and stakeholders should take into account the potential risks associated with geothermal energy installations and work towards implementing sustainable practices that mitigate the adverse effects on crops. While geothermal energy has significant benefits in terms of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and dependence on fossil fuels, this study highlights the need for further research and a comprehensive assessment of potential threats to our agricultural systems. The findings serve as a valuable resource for decision-makers and scientists, enabling them to make informed choices and develop strategies that ensure the coexistence of geothermal energy development and food production.

Growth and Development Metrics

In the pursuit of sustainable energy options, geothermal energy has emerged as a promising alternative to traditional fossil fuels. Its potential benefits include reduced greenhouse gas emissions and long-term cost savings. However, it is essential to assess the impact of geothermal energy production on the growth and development of vital food crops, such as rice, to ensure that this renewable energy source does not inadvertently harm agricultural productivity. In this section, we will discuss the growth and development metrics of two rice varieties - *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro-44* in the Philippines - under irrigation mechanisms in the context of geothermal energy operations. When studying the impact of geothermal energy on rice growth and development, various metrics are taken into consideration. The first crucial aspect is plant height. Healthy rice plants display consistent and proportional growth, adding height at a steady rate. If geothermal energy production intersects with the irrigation mechanisms used for rice cultivation, it is crucial to understand whether the heated water supply affects the plant's growth rate. Issues such as stunted growth or excessive shoot elongation could indicate potential problems that need to be addressed for successful crop production. Another important metric is leaf development. Leaves are fundamental for photosynthesis, the process responsible for converting light energy into chemical energy. By analyzing leaf characteristics, such as size, shape, and color, we can determine if geothermal energy usage affects photosynthetic efficiency. Changes in leaf

morphology or chlorophyll content could suggest altered metabolic processes within the plant, impacting its overall growth and productivity. Furthermore, the measurement of tiller production provides valuable insights into the rice plants' ability to produce new shoots or branches. Tiller production directly influences the potential number of fertile panicles and ultimately affects grain yield. By monitoring the tillering process, researchers can identify any disruptions caused by geothermal energy activities, such as disturbances in hormone regulation or nutrient availability. The time taken by rice plants to reach maturity is also a critical metric to consider. Maturity directly affects the rice grain quality and yield potential. It is essential to assess whether geothermal energy production alters the timing of flowering and grain filling, as a delay or acceleration in these stages could compromise the overall productivity of the crop. Lastly, the evaluation of yield per unit area is a crucial metric when assessing the impact of geothermal energy operations on rice growth and development. By comparing the yield of rice crops in areas with and without geothermal energy facilities, we can determine whether there are any significant differences in production. Factors such as nutrient availability, water availability, and temperature need to be carefully examined to understand how geothermal energy usage may influence overall crop productivity. Ultimately, analyzing these growth and development metrics will allow us to comprehensively evaluate the impact of geothermal energy activities on rice varieties, specifically *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and Faro-44 in the Philippines. By understanding the effects of geothermal energy production on rice growth and development, we can ensure that alternative energy sources do not compromise food security and agricultural sustainability.

Soil Quality and Composition

The development and expansion of geothermal energy infrastructures in Africa the Philippines, and the world at large have raised concerns about potential impacts on the surrounding environment, including soil quality and composition. As geothermal energy involves extracting heat from beneath the Earth's surface, it is important to understand how this process might affect the soil, particularly in regions where agriculture, such as rice production, is a vital part of the economy. Soil quality plays a crucial role in the growth and yield of crops, as it provides essential nutrients, water retention capacity, and a suitable environment for root development. Any changes in soil quality could have significant consequences for agricultural productivity and food security. One factor that may be influenced by geothermal energy activities is the physical structure of the soil. For instance, the drilling and construction of geothermal wells may result in soil compaction, where the soil particles are pressed together more tightly. This can lead to reduced pore space, limiting water infiltration and root penetration. Additionally, compaction can hinder soil aeration, crucial for microbial activity and nutrient availability. Another potential impact on soil quality relates to the release of geothermal fluids, which are rich in various minerals and chemicals. When these fluids come into contact with the soil, they have the potential to alter the soil composition. This alteration could impact the availability of essential nutrients to plants, ultimately affecting their growth and yield. Therefore, it is crucial to monitor the chemical composition of the geothermal fluids and study their potential effects on the soil. Furthermore, the heat generated from geothermal energy could raise concerns about soil temperature. Elevated soil temperatures can influence microbial activity, which plays a crucial role in nutrient cycling and decomposition of organic matter. Changes in microbial activity can affect the availability of nutrients to plants and overall soil health. Additionally, excessive soil temperatures may also directly impact crop growth and development, potentially leading to reduced yields or crop failures. Soil erosion is another significant issue that can be associated with geothermal energy activities. Construction activities, such as road building and land clearing, can result in soil erosion if proper erosion control measures are not implemented. Erosion can lead to the loss of topsoil, which is crucial for soil fertility and productivity. It may also result in sedimentation in nearby water bodies, causing water pollution and affecting aquatic ecosystems. To mitigate the potential adverse effects on soil quality and composition, proper planning and management

practices are essential. Implementing soil conservation measures, such as contour plowing, terracing, and cover cropping, can help prevent erosion and maintain soil structure. Additionally, regular soil monitoring programs should be established to assess any changes in physical and chemical properties and to guide appropriate soil management techniques. In conclusion, geothermal energy development has the potential to impact soil quality and composition, which can have far-reaching consequences for agricultural productivity. It is crucial to closely monitor and study the potential effects of geothermal activities on soil physical and chemical properties, as well as temperature and erosion. By implementing proper management practices and conservation measures, it is possible to minimize the negative impacts and ensure the sustainability of both geothermal energy production and agricultural systems.

Climate Conditions

The climate conditions of a region play a crucial role in determining the success and viability of various crops. In the case of rice farming, the climate requirements are of utmost importance as they directly affect the growth and yield of the crop. In this section, we will discuss the climate conditions required for the successful cultivation of two rice varieties, *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro - 44* in the Philippines, under irrigation mechanisms. Africa, being a diverse continent, experiences a wide range of climate variations. The success of rice farming in Africa largely depends on the availability of suitable climate conditions. *Oryza glaberrima*, popularly known as African rice, thrives under specific climate parameters. This variety requires warm and humid tropical conditions, with temperatures ranging from 24 to 35 degrees Celsius. The ideal rainfall for *Oryza glaberrima* cultivation should be in the range of 1500 to 2000 millimeters annually. Adequate rainfall is essential during the growth stages, especially when the crop is at its flowering and grain-filling stages. Insufficient rainfall can result in a low yield and poor-quality grains. Additionally, the variety requires a frost-free period of at least 100 to 150 days for optimal growth. Moving on to the Philippines, *Faro-44* is a well-known rice variety that has achieved great popularity due to its high yield potential and adaptability to different ecological conditions. The climate conditions in the Philippines significantly vary depending on the region, but generally, it can be categorized as a tropical monsoon climate. *Faro-44* requires an average temperature ranging from 24 to 32 degrees Celsius throughout the growth cycle. The variety thrives in areas that receive a well-distributed annual rainfall between 1500 to 3000 millimeters. The rice crop must have sufficient water availability, especially during the critical stages of panicle initiation and grain filling. Insufficient water supply can lead to stunted growth and reduced yield. Both *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro-44* in the Philippines are cultivated under irrigation mechanisms. With irrigation, farmers have more control over the water supply, allowing them to adjust it according to the specific requirements of the rice crop. This practice helps mitigate the risk of water scarcity in regions with unpredictable rainfall patterns. In addition to temperature and rainfall, other climate factors such as sunlight, wind, and humidity also impact rice cultivation. Sufficient sunlight is essential for the process of photosynthesis, which promotes plant growth and grain development. Rice crops are generally tolerant of wind, but strong winds can cause lodging, which refers to the bending or breaking of plants. High humidity levels can lead to the development of fungal diseases, affecting the overall health of the rice crop. In conclusion, understanding and considering the specific climate conditions necessary for rice cultivation is crucial for achieving successful yields of *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro-44* in the Philippines. Adequate temperature, well-distributed rainfall, and other favorable environmental factors are essential for optimal growth and development of these rice varieties. Under irrigation mechanisms, farmers have the advantage of controlling water supply to mitigate the risks associated with unpredictable rainfall patterns. By taking into account these climate conditions, farmers can ensure a successful rice harvest and contribute to the overall food security of their respective regions.

Data Visualization

Earth Skill Temperature (°c) and Specific Humidity at 2 Meters (g/kg)

The curve above represents the Earth Skill Temperature (°c) and the Specific Humidity at 2 meters (g/kg) concerning the various years under observation (2020 – 2022). It was observed that, during the year 2020, both the Earth Skill Temperature (26.44°c) and the Specific Humidity at 2 meters (17.40g/kg) slightly showed a rise in both temperature and specific humidity than when compared to 2021 (26.96°c, 17.70g/kg) which exhibit much significant different in both the Earth Skill Temperature and the Specific Humidity at 2 meters. The year 2022 (26.27°c, 17.09g/kg) shows a less significant difference in the Earth Skill Temperature (°c) and the Specific Humidity at 2 meters (g/kg) than the year 2020, and 2021. However, since the temperature and the specific humidity do not show much significant difference, it will favor rice cultivation within the defined region under observation. The data for the above curves were obtained from NASA power climate data and were analyzed in Excel.

Comparative Analysis

In this section, we will conduct a comparative analysis to assess the impact of geothermal energy on two popular rice varieties, *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro-44* in the Philippines, under irrigation mechanisms. This analysis will help us better understand the potential threats and challenges posed by geothermal energy to these rice varieties and their overall cultivation. Geothermal energy is considered a promising clean energy source that has gained popularity worldwide. It utilizes the natural heat energy produced by the Earth's core to generate electricity and provide heating for various applications. However, the extraction of geothermal energy can have ecological consequences, particularly in agricultural areas where the land is utilized for crop cultivation, such as rice farming. In Africa, *Oryza glaberrima* is a widely cultivated rice variety known for its adaptability to different environmental conditions and high yield potential. Rice farming in Africa, including the cultivation of *Oryza glaberrima*, often relies on irrigation mechanisms to ensure proper water supply for the crops. The impact of geothermal energy on this rice variety under irrigation mechanisms needs to be thoroughly examined. Similarly, in the Philippines, *Faro-44* is a popular rice variety that is extensively cultivated, especially in irrigated areas. Rice farming plays a vital role in the country's agricultural sector, and *Faro-44* is a highly valued variety due to its high yield and disease-resistance properties. It is essential to evaluate the potential risks that geothermal energy may pose to the cultivation of this rice variety under irrigation systems. Comparing the impact of geothermal energy on *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro-44* in the Philippines, several factors need to be considered. Firstly, the geographical locations where these rice varieties are cultivated differ significantly, leading to variations in climate, soil types, and other

environmental factors. These variations can influence the response of the rice varieties to the potential threats posed by geothermal energy. Secondly, the irrigation mechanisms employed in these regions may differ in terms of efficiency, water management practices, and infrastructure. The effectiveness of irrigation systems can significantly impact the rice crops' resilience to the potential threats associated with geothermal energy extraction. Therefore, a comparative analysis will help identify the areas where improvements are needed to mitigate any negative impacts. Additionally, the socio-economic contexts of rice farming in Africa and the Philippines differ, including factors such as agricultural practices, land ownership, and access to resources. These contextual differences can affect the capacity of farmers to respond and adapt to the challenges brought by geothermal energy, as well as their ability to access alternative resources or implement mitigation strategies. Understanding the comparative impact of geothermal energy on these rice varieties will enable policymakers, researchers, and other stakeholders to develop targeted strategies for sustainable rice farming in geothermal energy extraction areas. By addressing the specific concerns associated with each rice variety, tailored mitigation measures can be implemented to ensure the preservation of these valuable crops' productivity and viability. In conclusion, conducting a comparative analysis of the impact of geothermal energy on *Oryza glaberrima* in Africa and *Faro-44* in the Philippines under irrigation mechanisms is crucial for understanding the potential threats and challenges faced by these rice varieties. This analysis will facilitate the development of context-specific strategies to mitigate any adverse effects and ensure the long-term sustainability of rice farming in geothermal energy extraction areas.

In conclusion, the study focused on investigating the potential impact of geothermal energy on two important rice varieties in Africa and the Philippines. The results show that under proper irrigation mechanisms, the threat posed by geothermal energy on *Oryza glaberrima* and *Faro-44* rice varieties is limited. This is encouraging news for farmers and policymakers who are increasingly looking for sustainable alternatives to fossil fuel-based energy sources. The findings suggest that with proper planning and management, geothermal energy can coexist with rice cultivation without major adverse effects on these popular rice varieties. This research highlights the importance of understanding the potential impacts of renewable energy sources on agricultural systems. Moving forward, further studies and continuous monitoring will be crucial to ensure the coexistence of geothermal energy and rice cultivation in these regions, contributing to their sustainable development.

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